

Kinetics of Oxidation of Benzoic Acid by Peroxydisulphate Ion*

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Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of benzoic acid studies in H_2SO_4 medium has been found to be first order w.r.t. $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ and zero order w.r.t. benzoic acid. The specific rate decreases with $[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$ according to the relationship

$$-\log k = 2.5 + 23.2[S_2O_8^{2-}]_0$$

and increases with $(Ag^+)_0$ concentration according to $k = 0.25 \times 10^{-3} + 1.375(Ag^+)_0$. The salt effect is negative. The rate increases only slightly with (H^+) and strongly suppressed by allyl acetate. The mole ratio of benzoic acid : $S_2O_8^{2-}$ is 1 : 1.5. The energy parameters are $\Delta E = 7.86$ Kcal/mole, $A = 5.32$ litre mole⁻¹ sec.⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -57.39$ E.u. The specific ionic effect is in the following order :

A free radical chain mechanism has been suggested.

The uncatalysed and Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of various reductants have been carried out by various workers which have been recently reviewed by House¹. Besides its oxidising character peroxydisulphate ion is also well known to initiate polymerisation². Thus in the oxidation of benzoic acid by peroxydisulphate ion Bacon and Duggart³ have shown the formation of a resinous product which has approximate composition $(C_7H_5O_2)_n$. The present paper deals with our study of the kinetics of the hitherto unstudied oxidation of benzoic acid by peroxydisulphate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental set up was similar to that adopted in the study of the kinetics of oxidation of phthalic acid by peroxydisulphate ion⁴.

Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction in the absence of a catalyst was very very slow. However, in the presence of $AgNO_3$ as catalyst the reaction proceeds with measurable velocity at 55° and above.

Just as in the case of phthalic acid reaction, the self decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ has always been taken into consideration and the reaction has been carried out in 0.025 N H_2SO_4 medium to avoid precipitate formation for the period the reaction is under study.

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Effect of peroxydisulphate ion concentration : The effect of different initial concentrations of peroxydisulphate ion was studied at constant concentration of benzoic acid, AgNO_3 and H_2SO_4 , the results of which are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Benzoic Acid = 0.030M AgNO ₃ = 0.001M		H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.025M Temp. = 55°		
S.No.	Concn. of K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ (M)	$k' \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹	$k'' \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹	$k \times 10^3$ = $(k'' - k') \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹
1.	0.010	3.69	5.55	1.86
2.	0.015	3.77	5.14	1.37
3.	0.020	3.95	5.01	1.06
4.	0.025	4.05	4.81	0.76
5.	0.030	4.11	4.67	0.56

k'' is the specific rate in the presence and k' in the absence of benzoic acid.

From the data it is clear that the reaction follows first order behaviour at all concentrations of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ studied. The order w.r.t. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, determined by Vant Hoff's differential method using initial rate or by the time fractional method comes out to be one, indicating thereby that the order w.r.t. benzoic acid may be zero. However, in their study of the reduction of peroxydisulphate by benzoic acid Hermen and Cone⁵ have reported the appearance of two concurrent reactions—one first order' and the other second order w.r.t. peroxydisulphate.

The above data show that the first order rate constant decreases with the increase in peroxydisulphate ion concentration, according to the relationship

$$-\log k = 2.5 + 23.2[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]_0$$

Since in any particular run the specific rate does not decrease with time; hence this decrease in rate constant may be ascribed to the specific inhibitory effect of K^+ and not due to change in ionic strength C.f. observations on phthalic acid peroxydisulphate reaction⁴.

Effect of benzoic acid concentration : An examination of the data under Table 2 shows that the specific rate is not appreciably affected by a change in benzoic acid concentration.

TABLE 2

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.010M H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.025M		AgNO ₃ = 0.001M Temp. = 55°			
Concn. benzoic acid (M)	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.035	0.040
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.82	1.88	1.85	1.92	1.75

$$k' = 3.69 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}.$$

Effect of AgNO₃ concentration : Table 3 summarises the results of catalyst concentration on the rate of this reaction.

TABLE 3

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.010M		H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.025M		
Benzoic Acid = 0.030M		Temp. = 55°		
S.No.	AgNO ₃ concn. (M)	k' × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹	k'' × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹	k × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹
1.	0.0005	2.49	3.49	1.00
2.	0.0010	3.69	5.55	1.86
3.	0.0015	6.00	9.06	3.06
4.	0.0020	7.32	11.20	3.88
5.	0.0025	9.27	14.13	4.86

The specific rate is linearly related to the concentration of AgNO₃ by the expression

$$k = 0.25 \times 10^{-3} + 1.875 C_{Ag}^+$$

Effect of temperature : Table 4, summarises the kinetic results for five different temperatures and the values of energy parameters calculated therefrom.

TABLE 4

K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ = 0.010M					H ₂ SO ₄ = 0.025M			
Benzoic Acid = 0.030M					AgNO ₃ = 0.001M			
S.No.	Temp. °C	k' × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹	k'' × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹	k × 10 ³ min. ⁻¹	Temp. coeff.	$\frac{\Delta E}{\text{Kcal}} \frac{\Delta E}{\text{mole}^{-1}}$	A litre mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger E.u.
1.	45	1.92	3.22	1.30			5.33	-57.33
2.	50	2.60	4.20	1.60	1.42	7.29	5.37	-57.33
3.	55	3.69	5.55	1.86	1.40	7.12	5.18	-57.46
4.	60	5.20	7.42	2.22	1.52	9.20	5.19	-57.46
5.	65	7.24	10.07	2.83			5.54	-57.38
			Mean		1.44	7.86	5.32	-57.39

The abnormally low value of frequency factor suggests that :

- (i) Overall slowness of the reaction inspite of a rather low value of energy of activation.
- (ii) Atomic vibrations in the activated complex are the least⁶.
- (iii) The formation of activated complex involves either separation of opposite charges or an approach of like charges⁷.

The unusually large negative value of entropy of activation suggests that :

- (i) There is decrease in the degrees of freedom in the formation of the activated complex and therefore, it is a rigid one, as is also evident from the abnormally low value of frequency factor⁸.
- (ii) A small probability of the formation of the activated state, because every collision with the requisite amount of energy does not necessarily lead to the formation of activated complex⁹.

An abnormally low value of frequency factor and a large negative value of entropy of activation suggests that the formation of the activated complex in this reaction involves the redistribution of energy along various degrees of freedom in the reacting substrate which must be naturally a complex molecule.

Salt Effect : The effect of ionic strength was studied by using K_2SO_4 (concentration range upto $0.075M$) as the neutral salt.

The salt effect is found to be negative. However, it is neither primary exponential nor linear type. The exact nature of the salt effect could not be decided due to rather high ionic strength of the reaction medium ($H_2SO_4 = 0.025M$).

Effect of H^+ concentration : This effect was investigated by carrying out two sets of kinetic runs—one at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.33$) and the other at constant high concentration of H_2SO_4 ($0.1M$) with varying concentrations of K_2SO_4 , the results of these two sets are tabulated in Table No. 5.

TABLE 5

$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.010M$		$AgNO_3 = 0.001M$				
Benzoic acid = $0.025M$		Temp. = 55°				
$A - \mu = 0.33$	H_2SO_4 concn. (M)	0.025	0.040	0.050	0.075	0.090
	$[K_2SO_4]$ (M)	0.075	0.060	0.050	0.025	0.010
	$k'' \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	3.57	3.84	4.31	4.76	5.02
	$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	3.08	3.23	3.60	3.83	3.91
	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	0.49	0.61	0.71	0.93	1.11
$B - H_2SO_4 = 0.1 M$	K_2SO_4 concn. (M)	0.010	0.020	0.030	0.040	0.050
	$k'' \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	5.05	4.93	4.40	4.31	4.21
	$k' \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	3.86	3.81	3.36	3.35	3.31
	$k \times 10^3 \text{ min.}^{-1}$	1.19	1.12	1.04	0.96	0.90

A critical examination of the above two sets of data reveals that the specific rate in the two sets is related to K_2SO_4 concentration by the relationships

$$k = k_0 - 8.1 \times 10^{-3} [K_2SO_4] \quad \text{and} \quad k = k_0 - 7.5 \times 10^{-3} [K_2SO_4]$$

showing thereby that H^+ ions have very little catalytic effect, if any, on this reaction.

Specific ionic effect : The specific ionic effect was studied at low and constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.166$).

TABLE 6

Salt concn. (<i>M</i>)	$K_2S_2O_8 = 0.005M$				$AgNO_3 = 0.001M$			
	No salt	$H_2SO_4 = 0.050$	$ZnSO_4 = 0.0375$	$Na_2SO_4 = 0.050$	$K_2SO_4 = 0.050$	$MgSO_4 = 0.0375$	$Al_2(SO_4)_3 = 0.010$	$NaNO_3 = 0.150$
$k'' \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹	8.27	5.32	4.17	4.78	4.52	4.62	5.00	4.19
$k' \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹	6.28	3.56	3.26	3.21	3.09	3.84	4.35	3.69
$(k'' - k') \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹	1.99	1.76	0.91	1.57	1.43	0.78	0.65	0.50

Thus, the specific ionic effect is in the order of $NO_3^- > Al^{+3} > Mg^{+2} > Zn^{+2} > K^+ > Na^+ > H^+$.

Mole ratio : The mole ratio was determined by carrying out the reaction at high concentrations of peroxydisulphate (10 and 16 times of the concentration of benzoic acid). The reaction mixture in each set was taken in a number of test tubes at 55° and at different intervals of time the whole content from each test tube was analysed for unreacted peroxydisulphate. From these studies it was found that one mole of benzoic acid reacts completely with 1.5 moles of $K_2S_2O_8$.

Effect of allyl acetate : The reaction was completely suppressed when carried out in the presence of allyl acetate (0.12*M* and 0.15*M*).

DISCUSSION

The reaction is characterised by a low energy of activation, abnormally low value of frequency factor and large negative entropy of activation (C.f. observations on phthalic acid reaction⁴). However, the first order behaviour w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. benzoic acid and strong inhibitory effect of allyl acetate suggests that probably this reaction also follows a free radical chain mechanism :

The radicals $\text{OH}\cdot$ and $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ generated in the above three stages may be supposed to undergo a series of chain reactions with benzoic acid to yield polymeric products.

and so on.

The first three stages account for the general characteristics of the reaction, however, it has not been possible to work out the exact nature of the subsequent stages in which benzoic acid is involved.

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